

Physico-chemical Differentiation of the Gonadotropins: Prolan A and Prolan B

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A physico-chemical method of differentiating Prolan A from Prolan B is suggested herein by their interaction with *m*-xylohydroquinone. Although the reaction in both the cases are similar and associated with a peak at 260 m μ , the peak in the case of Prolan A is flat and extends from 258 m μ to 262m μ and that with Prolan B at 260 m μ) it is quite sharp.

It has already been reported¹ that chorionic gonadotropin reacts with *m*-xylohydroquinone, forming a complex with an absorption peak at 260 m μ . It has also been observed² that *m*-xylohydroquinone reacts with both D-galactose and D-glucosamine individually, constituting two components of the chorionic gonadotropin³⁻⁴. The resulting complexes, as observed in spectrophotometric studies¹, have absorption maximum exactly in the same region as in the former cases at 260 m μ , but the nature of the curves obtained is not exactly the same; it is slightly different. The complex formed by *m*-xylohydroquinone with D-galactose shows an absorption peak at 260 m μ ; the peak is sharp, whereas in the other case (*m*-xylohydroquinone with D-glucosamine) the maximum also occurs at 260 m μ , but the peak is rather flat⁴ (vide also curves I in Fig. 1 and 2).

It is already known that the chorionic gonadotropin has mainly lutenising effect yet it is able to cause hypertrophy of the interstitial ovarian tissue in the hypophysectomised rat, which is due to the fact that it contains a very small amount of follicle-stimulating hormone⁵ (FSH). Our previous work suggests that the main reaction of the chorionic gonadotropin with *m*-xylohydroquinone might be due to its reaction with lutenising hormone (LH) mainly.

Different views have been expressed by different workers regarding the role of this lutenising hormone (LH), but none appears to be satisfactory. The present work has been undertaken with a view to reopening the question and ascertaining its behaviour from studies on absorption in presence of *m*-xylohydroquinone in UV. Interaction of *m*-xylohydroquinone and serum gonadotropin [or equine gonadotropin, which behaves as the follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), is present in the pregnant mare's serum and not eliminated in the urine⁶] has also been studied spectrophotometrically and the results have been compared with our previous studies² in order to find out any similarity existing between them, and if so, to what it leads.

1. Sanyal and Ganguly, *Science & Culture*, 1954, 19, 356.
2. Sanyal *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 830.
3. Gurin *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 128, 528; 1940, 133, 467.
4. *Idem.*, *Science*, 1939, 89, 62.
5. Day and Rowlands, *J. Endocrinol.*, 1940, 255.
6. Leonard and Smith, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1933, 31, 283.

Prolan A represents serum gonadotropin, which is responsible for follicle-stimulating effect on the ovary (FSH) and is usually recovered from pregnant mare's serum (PMS).

Wave length (m μ)
FIG. 1

- 1—*m*-Xylohydroquinone ($3.909 \times 10^{-4}M$) +
D-galactose ($2.68 \times 10^{-2}M$).
2—*m*-XyloHq ($0.7 \times 10^{-4}M$) + Prolan B (500 I.U.)

Wave length (m μ)
FIG. 2

- 1—*m*-Xylohydroquinone ($3.714 \times 10^{-4}M$) +
D-glucosamine hydrochloride ($1.174 \times 10^{-2}M$).
2—*m*-Xylohydroquinone ($1.8494 \times 10^{-4}M$) +
Prolan A (200 I.U.) in 25 ml water.
3—Prolan A (200 I.U.) in 25 ml water.

Prolan B represents chorionic gonadotropin, which is responsible for the leutinising effect of the ovary (LH.) and is recovered from pregnant women's urine.

The object of the present paper is to offer an easy method of differentiation, by some physico-chemical approach, between the activities of these two gonadotropins because the biological methods are rather tedious and expensive.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dilute aqueous solutions of *m*-xylohydroquinone, chorionic gonadotropin Prolan B (pregnyl LH), and serum gonadotropin prolan A (gestyl) were prepared and their absorption curves studied both individually as well as in the mixtures of *m*-xylohydroquinone

and gestyl and *m*-xylohydroquinone and pregnyl. These data were compared with water as the solvent blank. Solutions of *m*-xylohydroquinone were prepared with special care to avoid its rapid oxidation in presence of light and air-oxygen. Each solution was therefore charged with nitrogen and preserved away from light.

The concentration of *m*-xylohydroquinone used in the mixture was $1.8494 \times 10^{-4} M$. Serum gonadotropin or gestyl or prolan A (200 international units) was dissolved in water and made to 25 ml. In another mixture the concentration of *m*-xylohydroquinone was $3.17 \times 10^{-4} M$ and that of D-glucosamine hydrochloride was $1.193 \times 10^{-2} M$. Concentrations refer to the final concentrations used in the mixture. Reference solutions of gestyl, pregnyl, and glucosamine hydrochloride were also prepared in the same concentrations. Each result was repeated thrice before it was accepted. Reagents were of pure quality and deoxygenated water was used throughout. Optical densities, determined with the help of a spectrophotometer, were plotted against wave length with solutions after 2 hr. of mixing (vide Fig. 1 and 2) and with those after 24 hours of mixing. Observations with the latter type of the mixtures had nothing particular to report upon. The behaviour was exactly similar to the mixture after 2 hours of mixing. The complex that is formed thus appears to be permanent or stable.

To test another interesting point in this connection in another set of experiments, a mixture of *m*-xylohydroquinone and γ -methyl-D-glucopyranoside was prepared with *m*-xylohydroquinone ($6.674 \times 10^{-4} M$) and the second component ($8.128 \times 10^{-4} M$) (Fig. 1). The curve obtained by plotting optical densities against wave length, was compared with that of a mixture of *m*-xylohydroquinone ($3.17 \times 10^{-4} M$) and D-galactose ($2.64 \times 10^{-2} M$) and D-glucose² and also with that of a mixture of *m*-xylohydroquinone ($3.17 \times 10^{-4} M$) and D-glucosamine hydrochloride ($1.93 \times 10^{-2} M$).

DISCUSSION

Numerous experiments, such as digestion by proteolytic enzymes, histological studies of the ovaries, and the endometrium of the uterus, etc., were designed by the biologists for the determination of the difference of reactions of the two types of gonadotropins, Prolan A (FSH) and Prolan B (LH). But none were quite conclusive. In the present case, however, the difference in the behaviour of these two types of gonadotropins (FSH and LH) would be easily detectable from spectrophotometric studies of their interaction with *m*-xylohydroquinone. In the case of chorionic gonadotropin (LH), the formation of a complex is indicated by a sharp absorption maximum at a region of 260 μ , whereas in the case of serum gonadotropin (FSH), the complex is indicated by a rather flat peak developing in the same region.

It is also interesting to note that the nature of the curve found in the interaction of D-galactose and *m*-xylohydroquinone is exactly similar to that of chorionic gonadotropin and *m*-xylohydroquinone. The absorption curve due to the interaction of D-glucosamine and *m*-xylohydroquinone is also similar to that of serum gonadotropin and *m*-xylohydroquinone. In the former case, the absorption maximum is sharp in the region of 260 μ , whereas in the latter, the absorption maximum is rather flat, the flat portion extending from 258 to 262 μ . These similarities in a way suggest that FSH activity might depend on D-glucosamine-protein complex and LH activity on the D-galactose-protein complex.

The responsibility of these sugars in these reactions was next examined. Obviously

there is a strong similarity of the absorption curves of the hormones (LH and FSH) with those of D-galactose and D-glucosamine (Fig. 1 and 2) respectively. As already mentioned^{2,3}, the sugar-protein complexes appear to be responsible for their reaction with *m*-xylohydroquinone, and to put it correctly, it is the sugar on which the whole responsibility of the reaction rests. To test this point, the reducing group was blocked by converting the sugar into α -methyl-D-glucopyranoside and then this was allowed to react with *m*-xylohydroquinone (Fig. 3). There was no reaction in this case, the peak in the absorption curve appearing at about 290 m μ , which marked the peak of *m*-xylohydroquinone alone (Fig. 3). So it appears that the reaction of the sugars with *m*-xylohydroquinone takes place with the reducing group of the sugar and also that in the protein-sugar complex, as present in the hormones, this reducing group is not affected.

FIG. 3. Wave length (m μ)
 Curve 1—*m*-Xylohydroquinone ($8.71 \times 10^{-4} M$) + glucosamine hydrochloride ($1.193 \times 10^{-2} M$).
 Curve 2—*m*-Xylohydroquinone ($6.674 \times 10^{-4} M$) + D- α -methyl glucopyranoside ($8.128 \times 10^{-4} M$).

D-galactose was kindly supplied by Dr. R. J. Boscott of Messrs. Pfizer Ltd., Kent, U.K. to whom the authors' grateful thanks are due; they express their sincere gratitude to Dr. A. K. Mitra for valuable suggestions and co-operation.